

	<p>Development of a protocol for biometric-based animal tracking and tracing</p>	

Muzzle Pattern as a Biometric Identifier for Cattle

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Introduction

In mammals, skin is covered with hair except in limited parts of the body such as palms in humans and muzzle in case of bovines. Muzzle (viz. snout or nose) patterns of cattle are uneven features of their skin surface. The arrangement and distribution of ridges and valleys are responsible for the formation of pattern on the muzzle. Baranov et al. (1993) indicates that the pattern of cattle muzzle is highly heritable and the asymmetry between muzzle halves is significant. Due to its uniqueness, the muzzle pattern can be considered as a biometric identifier. Because the muzzle pattern is consistent over time and individualistic like human fingerprints, it is used as a form of permanent identification. It is most commonly used for the sale and exhibition of sheep and cattle in USA. In Japan, in registration of beef cattle for breeding and marketing, the muzzle pattern is lifted on a piece of white paper in black ink within an age of 4 months and in an advanced registration at over 14 months old (Figure 1). More than 3 million beef cattle have been registered at Wagyu Registry Association in Kyoto since 1948 (Minagawa *et al.*, 2002).

Figure 1. Examples of muzzle patterns of an animal at the age of 2 months (left) and the same animal at the age of 14 months (right). Extracted from Minagawa *et al.* (2002)

1. Early investigations into muzzle ink printing of bovines

Only a few references are on record to point out the scope of muzzle print examination for identification. Petersen (1922) recognised the individuality of muzzle patterns and considered it as a means for identifying individual animals. Miller and West (1972) reported that nose prints, taken in the same manner as fingerprints, were used in New Zealand for the identification of cattle. This had some value in black-skinned animals, for which tattooing was of little help. Dellmann and Brown (1976) observed that the epidermis of the *planum nasolabiale* of dogs is thick and keratinised, and suggested that it might be used for identification. Pandey (1979) performed the first essential work on muzzle print examination. He took 500 pairs of prints of muzzle of cattle and buffaloes, irrespective of their age, sex or breed. These prints were examined qualitatively and quantitatively to differentiate one print from the other. The qualitative study of the print or M-printometry involved the measurement of relative distances and directions of the structures of the prints. When the structures on one print maintained exactly the same relationship with the structures of another print, both prints were considered identical and belonging to the same animal. The M-printometry was conducted in two ways: the triangulation method and the graphic method. In the triangulation method, three similar-looking structures were selected. These structures were named X, Y, and Z (belonging to print A), and X₁, Y₁ and Z₁ (belonging to print B). Then one ideal point was marked on each of the selected three structures of print A. These ideal points were named I, P, and S. The counter points of I, P and S were also marked in print B, and named as I₁, P₁ and S₁. Points I, P and S, and I₁, P₁ and S₁ were joined together to form one triangle on each print. The sides and angles of both triangles were measured. The sides of the triangles represent the relative distances between the structures and the angles represent the relative directions. When the sides and the angles of the triangle on print A were found identical to those of the triangle on print B, both prints were declared to be identical.

Pandey (1978) also examined muzzle prints taken at monthly intervals, and he pointed out that changes in prints with the lapse of time are negligible, and that changes in prints are most expected in calves up to 2 years of age, because of their high growth rate.

2. Muzzle patterns for differentiation of cattle traits

Graml et al. (1993) found out a significant association ($p < 0.05$) between linked casein genotypes and number of ridges and granulae of muzzle of 201 cows from Bavarian Simmental, Bavarian Brown, Tyrolean Grey and German Black and White breeds. Allele B from the β -casein locus showed a significant gene substitution effect relative to allele A². Additive genetic variance of the loci on muzzle pattern was estimated, and it accounted for 60-90% of the total genotypic variance. From this investigation, it appeared likely that the casein loci are linked to genes affecting the muzzle traits.

The analysis of the muzzle characteristics points towards the possibility of breed characterisation. Table 1 shows the differences in muzzle characteristics between six different breeds of cattle (Mishra et al., 1997). Likewise, Baranov et al. (1993) observed significant difference between breeds through muzzle characteristics.

Table 1. Mean values of muzzle characteristics of different breeds of cattle, showing statistical differences (Extracted from Mishra et al., 1997)

Muzzle characteristics		Breeds ¹					
		TH	SW	KS	KF	RW	BW
Beads	Base sector	58.9 ^a	55.6 ^a	68.6 ^b	59.8 ^a	35.9 ^c	40.0 ^c
	Middle sector	60.5 ^a	60.4 ^a	57.4 ^a	44.0 ^b	23.1 ^c	25.7 ^c
	Upper sector	127.4 ^a	127.0 ^a	124.6 ^b	125.6 ^a	85.0 ^c	92.1 ^c
	Total	246.8 ^{ab}	242.9 ^{ab}	267.9 ^a	228.7 ^b	143.8 ^c	157.2 ^c
Ridges	Right side	3.8 ^a	5.0 ^{ab}	4.6 ^a	5.3 ^{ab}	5.9 ^{ab}	6.8 ^b
	Left side	3.4 ^a	4.9 ^{ab}	4.5 ^a	5.5 ^{ab}	5.6 ^{ab}	6.9 ^b
Total ridges	In base sector	12.9 ^{ab}	9.9 ^a	12.1 ^a	13.4 ^{ab}	14.5 ^{ab}	15.5 ^b
	Middle sector	2.3 ^a	3.3 ^a	3.2 ^a	4.7 ^b	7.0 ^c	6.5 ^c
	Grand total	14.7 ^b	12.9 ^a	14.1 ^b	16.1 ^b	19.4 ^c	20.5 ^c
Pattern	Right side	2.1 ^a	2.3 ^a	2.4 ^a	2.8 ^a	2.7 ^a	2.3 ^a
	Left side	2.1 ^a	2.5 ^a	2.3 ^a	2.8 ^a	2.7 ^a	2.2 ^a
	Total	6.9 ^c	4.8 ^a	5.4 ^b	6.5 ^c	6.0 ^c	4.7 ^a

⁽¹⁾ TH, SW, KS, KF, RW and BW represent: Tharparkar, Sahiwal, Karan Swiss, Karan Fries, Red and White, and Black and White breeds, respectively.

a, b and c superscripts in a row differ significantly ($P < 0.05$).

Mishra and Dave (1989) correlated the number of beads present in the muzzle with the animal's age. The number of beads of the muzzle print was counted within an area of 2.5 x 2.5 cm. The coefficients of correlation between age and number of beads were highly significant for all muzzle sectors ($R > 0.906$), and they were negative values. In all the sectors, the number of beads declined with advancing age. However, the reduction was more marked up to 18 months of age. An important finding of this work is that after 42 months of age, the bead counts were almost constant.

3. Muzzle pattern classification

A system of muzzle classification was given by Mishra et al. (1996). During analysis of 602 muzzle prints (Table 2), they identified three structures: an oval, rounded or irregular structure spread over the muzzle were the "beads"; a straight or curved elongated structure arranged in specific manner over the muzzle were the "ridges"; and the "valley" was a clear space originating centrally at the base of the print and extending upwards to varying extent. They also observed that few ridges originate either from the central valley or from the same point located at the centre of the base line of the muzzle. Each ridge had different place of origin and arrangement but such ridges has common point of origin. These ridges were called "pattern ridges". On the basis of presence or absence of central valley (groove), the muzzle prints were classified into two main categories, i.e., grooved and non-grooved categories. Each of these categories was further classified into different classes by observing the distribution and arrangement of beads, ridges and pattern ridges. Apart from the two main categories, a very unlike pattern was also observed. Such muzzle prints were included into a third category called "special category".

3. 1 Patterns of Grooved Category

Alternate simple pattern ridge arrangement

In this pattern, only simple pattern ridges are observed. All simple pattern ridges are located exactly adjacent around central valley and arranged alternatively into right and left halves of the muzzle. The simple pattern ridge arrangement of this pattern is subject to

length of the appeared central valley. The pattern may or may not be extended to the middle of the muzzle print and depends on the magnitude of the central valley (Figure 2).

Table 2. Percentage of animals (n=602) in each category of muzzle patterns. Extracted from Mishra et al. (1996)

Categories	Percentage
A. Grooved category	
1. Alternate simple pattern ridge arrangement	51.83
2. Alternate compound pattern ridge arrangement	0.33
3. Pattern with simple and compound pattern ridge arrangement	1.99
4. Ridge distributed without pattern	1.83
5. Beads with no pattern	2.16
6. Pattern ridge arranged on top of central valley	0.17
B. Non-grooved category	
1. Alternate simple pattern ridge arrangement	20.26
2. Simple pattern ridge originating from same point	13.79
3. Pattern with simple and compound pattern ridge arrangement	1.33
4. Ridge distributed without pattern	3.98
5. Pattern only with beads	1.66
C. Special category	
1. Containing simple ridge	0.33
2. Containing compound ridge	0.17
3. Containing simple and compound ridge	0.17

Figure 2. Muzzle print sample belonging to alternate simple pattern ridge arrangement

Alternate compound pattern ridge arrangement

The arrangement of pattern ridge is very similar to the alternate simple pattern ridge arrangement. This pattern is based completely on the presence of compound pattern ridges. The compound ridges are wider and more intercepted than the simple ones. This is similar to the findings of Pandey (1979), where the muzzle was classified on the basis of simple and compound ridges. Simple pattern ridges are completely absent in this pattern (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Muzzle print sample belonging to alternate compound pattern ridge arrangement

Pattern with simple and compound pattern ridge arrangement

This pattern consists of a combination of simple and compound pattern ridges. The simple and compound pattern ridges are located explicitly adjacent to central valley (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Muzzle print sample belonging to alternate simple and compound pattern ridge arrangement

Ridge distributed without pattern

Due to the complete absence of pattern ridges, no specific arrangement is observed. The ridges have no explicit origin and are distributed on the surface relief of the muzzle. These ridges are called “distributed ridges” (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Muzzle print sample belonging to ridge distributed without pattern

Beads with no pattern

Complete absence of pattern ridge and distributed ridges are observed in this type of pattern. Only beads are available and distributed on the muzzle. The central valley is present and divides the muzzle into right and left halves. This pattern was also reported by Trofimenko (1988), where he classified such pattern as granular (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Muzzle print sample belonging to beads with no pattern

Pattern ridge arrangement from the top of central valley

The beads, distributed ridges and pattern ridges are present in this pattern, but the peculiar arrangement is entirely different from the rest of the patterns. Most of the pattern ridges are arranged on the top or end point of the central valley, and a few pattern ridges show their origin from either side of the central valley (Figure 7).

3.2 Patterns of non-grooved category

The central valley is completely absent in this category. The pattern ridges originate very often from the centre of the muzzle. The muzzle is divided into right and left halves due to arrangement and course of the pattern ridges to their respective direction. In case of

patterns formed by distributed ridges as well as those formed by beads only, the muzzle is not divided into right and left halves.

Figure 7. Muzzle print sample belonging to pattern ridge arrangement from the top of the central valley

Alternate simple pattern ridge arrangement

The simple pattern ridges of different characteristic features, shapes and types are arranged alternatively. The arrangement of pattern ridge in this category is quite close to alternate simple pattern ridge arrangement of the grooved category, with the major difference being the absence of the central valley. The simple pattern ridge must be examined for its location and point of origin at the central area of the muzzle print to decide whether this pattern actually belongs to an alternate simple pattern ridge arrangement of non-grooved category. If such is not the case, the muzzle can never be classified into this pattern. The pattern ridges of this category originate from centre and course towards the sides of the muzzles. Such coursing of the pattern ridges causes the division of muzzle into right and left halves (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Muzzle print sample belonging to alternate simple pattern ridge arrangement

Simple pattern ridge originating from same point

This is the most peculiar pattern among all categories. The arrangement of pattern ridges is not alternate; rather, they are located at the same point and distributed from the centre of the muzzle. No demarcation between right and left halves can be made (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Muzzle print sample belonging to alternate simple pattern ridge originating from the same point

Pattern with simple and compound ridge arrangement

Simple and compound pattern ridges are present in this category (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Muzzle print sample belonging to pattern with simple and compound ridge arrangement

Ridge distributed without pattern

The pattern ridges are absent in this category. This pattern is similar to the “ridge distributed without pattern” of the grooved category, except for the absence of the central valley (Figure 11).

Pattern only with beads

Only beads are seen in this pattern. Complete absence of pattern ridges, distributed ridges, and central valley were the distinguishing features of this category (Figure 12).

3.3 Patterns of special category

The special category has three main patterns: muzzle containing simple ridges, containing compound ridges and a combination of simple and compound ridges. The peculiarity of the patterns of the special category is the distinct and irregular arrangement of ridges on the muzzle (Figure 13).

Figure 11. Muzzle print sample belonging to ridge distributed without pattern

Figure 12. Muzzle print sample belonging to pattern only with beads

Figure 13. Samples of muzzle prints belonging to special category: simple ridge (A), compound ridge (B), and simple and compound ridge (C). Extracted from Mishra et al. (1996)

4. Coding for individual identification of cattle

Mishra et al. (1998) developed a method for individual identification of cattle, based on their earlier system of muzzle pattern classification (Mishra et al., 1996). According to their method, the muzzle print of each animal is divided into three standard sectors by dividing the total area of the muzzle into a 2:1:2 ratio to base, middle and upper sectors. The number of beads and ridges and pattern ridges available on each sector of the muzzle prints are counted and recorded separately. The pattern ridges are characterised by a measure of the angle of origin.

4.1 Angle measurement of pattern ridges

The number of pattern ridges is traced on the muzzle print for right and left halves, in case they are arranged around a central valley. If the pattern ridges originate from the same point, the recording is made from right to left in counter clock-wise direction. The point of origin of the pattern ridge and its point of deviation from normal course are marked, and a line is traced. Thus, the angle of the pattern ridge is the angle between the line and a horizontal line (Figure 14).

Figure 14. Measurement of angles formed by pattern ridges, according to Mishra et al. (1998).

4.2 Coding muzzle sectors

Base sector:

An alphabetic code – representing an angle – for the pattern ridges of the right side are written in numerator position and the ones of the left side are written in denominator position.

Middle sector:

Very frequently some pattern ridges extend up to the middle sector. Such pattern ridges are called “extended pattern ridges” in the middle sector and are used to develop the code together with the number of beads in the middle sector. The angles of right and left extended pattern ridges are measured in the same way as for the base sector (Figure 14).

Upper sector:

Due to the lower individual variation in the upper sector, the only attribute to codify is the number of beads.

5. Methodology for muzzle printing

Mishra et al. (1994) found that the cyclostyle ink procedure was the best technique for muzzle printing. The materials required in this procedure are the following:

- a. Printing ink: the black print ink of smooth texture and free from lumps should be used. This ink should have a consistency suitable for rolling into a thin film and quick drying when transferred to paper.
- b. Roller: a soft roller, 15 to 18 cm long is recommended. The handle of the roller should have a supporting peg to suspend the rubber roller in air when not in use.
- c. Slab: a piece of aluminium plate, with smooth edges and surface, is used for the preparation of homogeneous film of ink.
- d. Metal pad: A metal pad of 30 cm long and 15 cm wide, with an appropriate curve is recommended. A hard and good quality foam, of the same size as the metal pad

- should be adhered on the metal pad. The metal device should have means of paper attachment on both ends.
- e. Antiperspirant: Mishra et al. (1994) recommend the use of antiperspirant to control muzzle sweating, and it should be applied after cleaning and washing the muzzle.
 - f. Printing paper: Quality bond paper should be used.

5.1 Protocol for muzzle printing

A thin homogeneous film of ink is prepared on the cleaned and smooth surface of the slab with the help of the clean roller. The metal pad is kept ready by fixing printing paper on it. The muzzle is then washed and dried with a cotton towel. Antiperspirant is then spread to check sweating. Then, the muzzle is again cleaned with the towel to remove sweat and excessive antiperspirant adhered on the muzzle. The slab impregnated with printing ink is applied on the muzzle by holding firmly the head of the animal. Uniform distribution of ink on the muzzle surface should be made. The metal pad with paper attached is then driven from base to top of the muzzle. The paper is then removed from the metal pad and allowed to dry.

Problems associated with nose printing include: the use of too much ink, a build-up of moisture on the animal's nose, and not holding the animal still, can result in a smeared, unreadable print (Neary and Yager, 2002).

5.2 Precautions for muzzle printing

- The slab and roller should be kept free from dirt and dust.
- The slab and roller should be cleaned with laboratory alcohol.
- Care should be taken to avoid excessive use of ink. Only a small quantity of ink is used to prepare homogenous thin layer of ink. To control the ink film thickness, it is recommended to do a cross rolling.
- The roller is driven each time on the slab to prepare new film for every muzzle print.

- The nostrils should be plugged with cotton before application of antiperspirant in order to avoid inhalation.

Although this method of identification has proven to be highly accurate, its main disadvantage is the length of time to take the print and the difficulty in obtaining it. Fitzgerald (2004) reported that the time to obtain a good muzzle printing per animal could reach up to 6 minutes.

6. Methods for muzzle pattern recognition

To determine a positive match between two muzzle prints, Blomeke et al. (2004) point out that at least five consecutive structures must be found between prints (Figure 15).

Minagawa *et al.* (2002) attempted to employ some simple image enhancing and feature extraction technique to identify beef cattle automatically through muzzle patterns printed in paper. They determined a square area for image analysis, based on the minimum length between the nostril borders of the sample (Figure 16). After applying techniques of filtering, binary transforming, thinning, and feature extraction, their technique was able to reach only 68% of correct animal identification.

Niu and Sasaki (1993) proposed an automated recognition method for muzzle prints. The descriptors of the muzzle pattern are eight parameters given in a vectorial form: ridge area, location, complexity, main axis direction, elongation, eccentricity and the coordinates of gravity centre. The identification of a muzzle print is performed by both a decision tree and structural analysis.

Figure 15. Examples of beef cattle nose prints where five consecutive points determine positive match (Blomeke *et al.*, 2004)

Figure 16. Image analysis area of muzzle pattern used by Minagawa *et al.* (2002)

Kimura et al. (2004) proposed a pattern recognition method applicable to biological textures undergoing deformations during the individual growing stage. Specifically, they focus on cattle muzzle patterns as an example of a biological texture and select graph matching based on a horizontal search as the basic strategy to create this new recognition system consisting of a technique for determining a pair of Hough-transformed search-starting cycles and a muzzle pattern recognition method that improves search efficiency by incorporating processing for merging non-searched cycles.

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